

POROČILO O IZVEDBI ŠTUDIJSKEGA OBISKA V TUJINI**FINANCIAL & ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT H2020/HEU”****(11. – 12. 10. 2023; Bruselj, Belgija)****Izvajalec: EFMC (European Fund Management Consulting | www.efmc.eu)****Udeleženka: Mira Metljak, NIB****Nelektorirano gradivo.**

V oktobru 2023 sem se v okviru projekta 5xPRO udeležila izobraževanja v tujini z naslovom Financial and administrative management H2020/HEU. Izobraževanje je potekalo 2 dni po 8 ur (9.00 – 17.00). Spodaj prilagam kratke poudarke izobraževanja. Predstavitve predavatelja so zaščitene in se jih ne sme distribuirati in/ali javno objavljati (»Any reproduction, republication, distribution, or redistribution of EFMC presentations and material is strictly prohibited under Estonian national law.»).

11. 10. 2023 – prvi dan usposabljanja (9.00 do 17.00)

Prvi dan smo obravnavali splošne vsebine glede črpanja sredstev Evropske unije. Nato smo obravnavali različne oblike financiranja (actual, unit, flat rate, lump sum) ter podrobneje pogledali stroške osebja (za različne oblike in različno metodologijo). Vse vsebine smo vzporedno pogledali za H2020 projekte ter razlike do HEU projekte. Predavatelj nas je predvsem opozoril na posebnosti in na najpogostejše napake, na katere moramo biti pozorni. Predstavil je tudi dileme, ki se pojavljajo in predstavil nekaj praks, ki nam lahko pomagajo pri razrešitvi teh dilem (npr. kater sistem izračunavanja urnih postavk izbrati; metodologija za pretvorbo ur v dneve).

AGENDA DAY 1**01 / GENERAL OVERVIEW***General overview, EU Budget, introduction to Horizon Europe, Statistics of H2020*

Predavatelj je predstavil trenutno sestavo in ozadje evropske komisije. Trenutna komisarka za Innovation and Youth je Iliana Ivanova.

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Poleg Directorate-General for Research and Innovation se z razvojem in raziskovanjem ukvarjajo še druga EU telesa, in sicer: *Joint Research Centre (DG JRC); European Research Council (ERC); European Innovation Council (EIC) in European Institute of Innovation & Technology.*

Finančni okvir je trenutno za leta od 2021-2027. Predstavil nam je strukturo proračuna za posamezna področja. Trenutno gre veliko sredstev za kmetijstvo v širšem smislu in regionalni razvoj. Horizon Europe (HEU) je le del finančnega okvirja.

Od Horizon 2020 do Horizon Europe (HEU) – spremenjena logika. HEU je, glede na H2020, impact driven (What will be the impact in the future.). Nato je predavatelj predstavil še vrste shem.

Types of actions & funding rates

Pillar I: 23,2 B€

- **Training and mobility action (MSCA)** → Unit costs
- **ERC Grants** → 100% funding rate & (indirect= 25% of direct costs)

Pillar II: 47,5 B€

- **Research and innovation actions (RIA):** establish new knowledge and/or to explore the feasibility of a new or improved technology, product, process, service or solution. **Basic and applied research, technology development** and integration, **testing and validation** on a **small-scale prototype** in a laboratory or simulated environment. 100% funding rate & (indirect = 25% of direct costs)
- **Innovation actions (IA)** → activities directly aiming at **producing plans and arrangements or designs** for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. **Prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication** → 70% funding rate & (indirect= 25% of direct costs)
- **Coordination and support actions (CSA)** → accompanying measures such as **standardisation, dissemination, awareness-raising and communication, networking, coordination or support services, policy dialogues and mutual learning** exercises and

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studies, including design studies for new infrastructure and may also include complementary activities of strategic planning, networking and coordination between programmes in different countries 100% funding rate & (indirect= 25% of direct costs)

Pillar III: 11,7 B€

- **EIC Pathfinder** →100% funding rate & (indirect= 25% of direct costs)
- **EIC Transition**→100% funding rate & (indirect= 25% of direct costs)
- **EIC Accelerator** →70% funding rate & (indirect= 25% of direct costs)
- **EIT Framework Partnership Agreement / Specific Grant Agreement**

ERA-NET Co-fund actions →33%

European Joint Programme (EJP) Co-fund action →70%

Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) →30% (25% indirect)

Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI) →30% (25% indirect)

Prizes →lump sum

Nato je bila predstavljena tudi statistika za projekte H2020.

02 / LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF A HORIZON ACTION

The grant, consequences of not fulfilling GA obligations

Predstavljene so bile glavne napake, ki se pojavljajo pri poročanjih in vplivajo tudi na spremembe v AMGA.

H2020 – Grant agreement (GA) + 6 aneksov; HEU Grant agreement (data sheet) + 5 aneksov.

Višina dodeljenih sredstev: **maximum / final / revised**

The fact that the beneficiary has completed the project does not ensure the right to get the EU contribution.

- 1) Maximum= never be exceeded
- 2) Final= before balance
- 3) Revised= after balance

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CFS – na posameznega partnerja, na koncu projekta.

Posledice, če ne izpolniš obljub iz GA:

- Zavrnitev stroška (kršenje pravil glede upravičenih stroškov),
- Znižanje dodeljenih sredstev (velike napake - SUBSTANTIONAL ERRORS (napaka), nepravilnosti - IRREGULARITIES (interes firme), prevare - FREUD (privatni interes)),
- Administrativne sankcije.

Lahko poročaš več stroškov, kot si upravičen (napram EC), smiselno ker:

- Če si zapravil več, kot ti pripada/si dobil in imaš po projektu audit, kjer ugotovijo, da moraš kaj vrniti, ti ne bo treba vrniti, ker si zapravil več, kot si dobil oz. boš vrnil samo do razlike, kolikor si zapravil.
- V H2020 možen prenos med partnerji brez amandmaja (npr. če se na koncu ugotovi, da je nekdo zapravil več, drugi pa manj, kot je bilo v planu).
- Kot informacija za naprej – če npr. vedno več zapraviš, je morda smotrno pogledati, če je kakšna sistemska napaka pri prijavljanju FN.

03 / ELIGIBLE AND NON-ELIGIBLE EXPENDITURE

Eligibility criteria per form of cost (Actual, Unit, Lump sum, Flat Rate), Direct vs. Indirect costs

ACTUAL COST (Actually incurred by the beneficiary - therefore - as registered in the beneficiary accounts.) / UNIT COST (An amount that must be multiplied by a number of Units (used) in order to calculate the eligible amount.) / FLAT RATE (The cost is calculated using a pre-defined percentage applied to an amount.) / LUMP SUM (A global amount covering all costs of the action/category.)

ELIGIBILITY CINDITIONS = strošek mora nastati tekom projekta; 3 izjeme:

- Stroški za kick off (ki mora biti organiziran v času trajanja!), če so nastali pred pričetkom projekta (npr. nakup letalske karte);
- Stroški dela za pisanje tehničnega in administrativnega poročila (60 dni po koncu);
- CSF potrdilo.

(Način knjiženja stroškov lahko vpliva na eligibility – knjiženje na podlagi datuma izdaje naročila / plačila / dobave – pomemben datum – ali v času projekta ali izven.)

Če nekega stroška v FN nisi predvidel, tudi kasneje ne moreš prenašati na tisto postavko.

UNIT COST je opcija od ACTUAL COST in se opredeli v Aneksu (to se uporabi, če je stalna praksa institucije, da za določene stroške uporablja UC).

NOVO - LUMP SUM – zelo pomembno kako se pripravi konzorcijska pogodba!

- **NO** Financial checks, reviews, or audits!
- **YES** Checks, reviews, and audits will focus on the technical implementation of the action.

DIRECT vs. INDIRECT COSTS

- DIRECT → directly linked to the action implementation, and can be directly attributed to it.
- INDIRECT → linked but cannot be directly attributed to the action implementation (are not, or can not be measured and attributed to the action e.g. overheads).

Definitely and Always indirect

- General management
- Registry
- Human Resources
- Legal Department
- Libraries
- Communications
- Procurement
- Postage
- Administrative, clerical staff
- General Water and Electricity
- Desktop computer and telephones
- Insurances
- Maintenance of equipment

NOT Always indirect

- General IT
- Office space
- Basic Lab materials
- Electricity for ex. cleanrooms

Pametno je, da je PP organizirana na način – PRE and POST AWORD, saj PRE aword strošek sodi pod indirect costs, POST pa lahko v direct. Pomembno tudi, kako je PP organizirana. Če na splošno PP sodi pod skupne službe (ki je financirana oz. organizirana kot posredni stroški), potem to ne more biti direct cost za projekt.

04/DIRECT COSTS -PERSONNEL COSTS

Novelties introduced by the corporate approach (H2020 vs. HEU), Type of personnel, Calculation of the personnel costs

PERSONNEL COSTS (ne nujno EMPLOYEE!)

a) H2020 metodologija za employees

Strateška odločitev za katero metodo se odločiš pri računanju stroškov osebja za zaposlene (employee):

- Lahko letno (zadnje zaključeno leto – so lahko izgube)
- Lahko mesečno (če je veliko zaposlenih, je to težje izvedljivo)

Metodologijo se lahko spremeni v novem letu.

Change?

Next Financial Year

For all personnel

For all H2020 grants

DOUBLE CILING RULE!

1. **Total costs** declared **NOT higher** than costs registered in the accounts (per person per year)
2. **Hours declared** **NOT higher** than Annual Productive Hours (option) used to calculate the H/R

Letna urna postavka:

$$f = \frac{\text{annual personnel costs (excluding additional remuneration)}}{\text{annual productive hours}}$$

Letne productive hours – 3 opcije:

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- 1720 (problem, če je poročanih ur manj); fixed hours – Same for all personnel,
- Individual (problem, če je zaposlenih veliko); number of hours worked by the person – One per person,
- Standard (workable hours / productive hours); generally applied by the beneficiary – Same for all personnel.

Same “option” to all personnel, or different option for **different type of personnel**, if:

- At least per **group of personnel** under similar contract,
- Applied **consistently**.

Mesečna urna postavka

$$f = \frac{\text{actual monthly costs (excluding additional remuneration)}}{\frac{1}{12} \text{ annual productive hours}}$$

Predstavljene so bile tudi specifike za izračune, npr. odsotnosti, nadure, ...

Hourly rate using UNIT COSTS

COMUC = Certificate on the Methodology of Unit Costs

Uporabljaš, če se standardno uporablja v podjetju na tak način.

2 / ELIGIBLE & NON-ELIGIBLE COSTS

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Main novelties introduced

H2020	Horizon Europe
Action type specific	Corporate model
Hourly Rate	Daily Rate
Financial Year	Reporting period
Annual/Monthly	1 per reporting period
1720/Individual/Standard (hours)	215 (days)
N/A	3 options
Monthly timesheets	Monthly declaration of Days

Model of GA
Rate for personnel costs
Calculation of the rate
Options for rate calculation
Productive time for rate calculation
Conversion rate Hours → Days
Time record keeping

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b) HEU metodologija za employees

Daily rate.

Dneve je treba zaokrožiti na 0,5; a glede na 0,25 interval (po se zaokroži navzdol, nad navzgor).

3 opcije za konverzijo hours to days:

- Fixed,
- Average (productive!),
- The higher between.

Predstavljeni so bili načini izračunavanja dnevnih urnih postavk. Posebnosti ipd.

A2. Natural persons working under direct contract A3. Seconded personnel

A2 – Natural person under direct contract (izda račun lastne firme) – PAZIŠ, kako pripraviš pogodbo (če pogodba ni OK, gre potem ta strošek pod A4 ali A5 (kjer so pa določeni zneski)); opredeliti treba strošek na uro (urno postavko) in določiti delovni čas. DELAJO V TVOJIH PROSTORIH NA VSEBINI PROJETA POD ENAKIMI POGOJI KOT TVOJI ZAPOSLENI. (Gre npr. za

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določena svetovanja, ...). PAZI na nacionalno zakonodajo, saj lahko meji na zaposlitev, na kar se lahko oseba pritoži.

A.3 Seconded personnel

- Must be formally seconded (secondment agreement).
- NO between beneficiaries: the seconding organisation declares its costs.

A4. SMEs owners & Natural persons not receiving a salary

12. 10. 2023 – drugi dan usposabljanja (9.00 do 17.00)

Drugi dan smo začeli s pomembno temo, kot je predstavil predavatelj, in to je sistem beleženja ur. Poudaril je, da je izjemno pomembno, da je sistem zanesljiv in da ne omogoča naknadnega spreminjanja oz. prirejanja podatkov. Nato je predstavil še vse ostale stroške, ki nastajajo tekom projekta in so upravičeni do financiranja (predvsem je pomembno, da prepoznamo, kakšno vlogo imajo zunanji partnerji/izvajalci, da se potem ustrezno beleži stroške oz. vrsto stroška). Podal je tudi konkretne primere glede uveljavljanja amortizacije in nakupa opreme (kje se največkrat pojavljajo dileme in možne predloge rešitev). Na koncu smo imeli še vsebine, ki so zajemale vloge in naloge posameznega partnerja v konzorciju in kako pomembno je, da je konzorcijska pogodba dobro napisana ter da vključuje vse vidike sodelovanja oz. vire morebitnih konfliktov (še bolj pomembno bo to verjetno sedaj, ko prehaja financiranja na Lump Sum metodologijo).

AGENDA DAY 2

01/ DIRECT COSTS - PERSONNEL COSTS

Time Recording System (TRS)

TIME RECORDING SISTEM!!!

- Must be reliable – ko enkrat vneseš, se podatkov ne da več spreminjati (oz. lahko spremeniš samo sam oz. z dovoljenjem zaposlenega).
- Minimum requirements!!!

The **title** and the **number of the action**.

The beneficiary's full name.

The full **name**, the **date** and **signature** of the **person working** for the action.

The full **name**, the **date** and **signature** of the supervisor.

The **number of hours worked** for the action in the period.

A reference to the action **tasks** or **WP** of Annex 1.

- Supervisor – tisti, ki dejansko ve oz. lahko potrdi, da si delal za projekt xy ur (npr. project manager).

HEU – dated & signed at least monthly by the person & supervisor (mora biti v notranjih pravilih – npr. do 10 v naslednjem mesecu); lahko se podpiše digitalno, če ni možnih naknadnih sprememb (npr. IT department).

- Templates – DON'T use IT (če imaš samo to) - predstavil je primere časovnic.
 - Ne morejo preverjati ur na drugih (nonEU) projektih.
 - Podpisi/datumi – skratka, ne sme zgledati, kot da je »pripravljeno«; npr. vsi podpisi zadnjega v mesecu/ oba podpisa vedno na isti dan.
 - HEU nima več možnosti 1 časovnice za celo obdobje, če si 100% zaposlen.
- = SISTEM, KI NE OMOGOČA PREVAR!

02/ OTHER DIRECT COSTS*Possible stakeholders in a project*

1) AFFILIATED ENTITIES – capital or legal link (če npr. delajo na svoji instituciji; če bi pa eden od njih prišel na našo institucijo npr. 1 x na teden in tam opravljal delo, bi pa bila to linked third party – dobijo pa lahko sredstva samo za plačo tega zaposlenega (drugih stroškov pa ne); lahko pa je for free). Pomembna je LOKACIJA opravljanja dela!

Lahko si enkrat partner, drugič pa affiliated entity – odvisno, kako veliko vlogo imaš v projektu.

HEU:

- Have their own financial statement,
- Must provide their own CFS,
- Must contribute to the technical report,

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- Must submit deliverables.

2) ASSOCIATED PARTNERS (NO EU MONEY)

3) IN-KIND CONTRIBUTORS

Against payment & Free of charge

How they contribute?

- A3) Seconded personnel,
- C2) Equipment,
- C3) Goods and Service.

Subcontracting

Subcontractors are external suppliers of Services, consisting in “project tasks”. They conduct part of the research project against a market fee (cost + profit).

Vključeni v technical part of the project (vsebina).

Če so zneski veliki, ne moreš vedeti že v naprej, kdo bo subcontractor; edino, če imaš skupno JN in vse določene naloge opravlja izbrani.

NO to:

- project partners,
- affiliates (except framework contract/ usual provider and is priced at market conditions),
- for coordination tasks.

Financial support to 3rd parties

Subgrantees – omejena vrednost.

Purchase of goods and services (Travel, consumables, services)

Travel costs and related subsistence allowances:

- Travels, allowances (+ related duties, taxes, etc),
- Beneficiary’s Travel Policy or usual practice,
- Must be **necessary** for the results,

- **Only as actual costs** (unless it is a Lump Sum),
- Travel outside Europe not accepted unless indicated in Annex 1.

Lahko tudi za tiste, ki niso zaposleni pri tebi (ANEX 1!!!)

All employees must be assigned to the project!!! (ali pa če so že napisani v grant agreementu/application) – če želiš za njih uveljavljati TC.

Lahko je to samo mail – brez ur = you have been assigned to the project xy nu 123 ...

Če si assigned, moraš pisati časovnice, tudi če z 0 urami, za celo obdobje poročanja (če izpolniš npr. eno/dve, ko si šel na neko pot).

Je pa smiselno, da daš vsaj nekaj PC costs, da se ve, da je linked to a project.

Contractors are external suppliers of non-core (research) Services, Goods, Works against a market fee (cost + profit). Their services are not research, but they are necessary for the proper implementation of the action).

- catering, odvetnik, CSF, prevod (contracts)

PURCHASE OF GOODS & SERVICES

These are costs that **do not cover the core of the action**, but are **necessary** for its correct implementation

If the usual accounting practice the Beneficiary considers some or all of these costs as indirect costs, they fall into category (E) and cannot be declared as direct costs. (Če je nekaj v običajni praksi indirect cost/overheads, potem tudi pri projektu ne more biti drugače.)

Equipment

4 types of equipment costs:

- Depreciation** costs of Assets,
- Full purchase costs**,
- Renting/leasing**,
- In-kind contribution** against payment.

(Če je nekaj v običajni praksi indirect cost/overheads, potem tudi pri projektu ne more biti drugače.)

The cost **cannot**

- **exceed the purchase price** of the equipment,

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- be spread over period **longer than useful life**,
- be charged for **period before the purchase** of the equipment,
- if the equipment's **useful life is more than a year**, total costs **cannot be charged in a single year** (unless the GA explicitly foresees this option).

Če prodaj pred koncem, moraš to »prijaviti« kot income; predlaga, da prodaj po zaključenem finančnem letu (se pravi, leto po zaključku).

Internal invoicing

Exchange rate

- če si EU, vzameš kar želiš,
- če si drugo, potem je portal in vzameš average na reporting period; če ni na portalu, je na drugem seznamu, kjer pa vzameš vsak mesec posebej.

Daily euro exchange rate is published in the C series of the **Official Journal of the European Union** for the currency in question: using the **average** of the daily exchange rates published over the corresponding reporting period.

http://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/policy_and_exchange_rates/euro_reference_exchange_rates/html/index.en.html

If NO daily euro exchange rate is published: using the **average of the monthly accounting rates** over the corresponding reporting period, using the currency converter on the Commission's website.

http://ec.europa.eu/budget/contracts_grants/info_contracts/inforeuro/index_en.cfm

Receipts (incomes)

Incomes generated during (and by) the action e.g.:

- **sale of assets**,
- **revenues** of a conference (fees),
- **financial contributions given by third parties** specifically to be used for the action (i.e. money given as a donation by a third party (a donor) to a beneficiary/linked third party specifically for the action covered by the GA),

- **in-kind contributions provided by third parties free of charge** specifically to be used for the action, if they have been declared as eligible costs.

03/ ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT

Coordinator rights & obligations

Beneficiaries obligations

- Coordinator ne sme vsiljevati stvari, saj je vsak partner sam odgovoren za svoj budget in poročanje.
- V konzorcijski pogodbi skušaj predvideti vse možne težave in jih »rešiti« oz. predvideti rešitve/ukrepe.
- Financial riability check pred prijavo – mogoče za vse partnerje v času priprave projekta (je zastonj; preveriš finančno stabilnost potencialnega partnerja v projektu).

Consortium Agreement

- Sodišče lahko daš katerokoli (EU država) – on predlaga Luksemburg (je pa dobro, da iz nobene od partnerskih inštitucij).
- Lump Sum – potrebuješ res močno konzorcijsko pogodbo!!!

Legal aspects: IPR, Conflict of interest, Confidentiality

IP management should be **additionally (to the GA) arranged in the CA.**

Pomoč: [European IP Helpdesk \(https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en\)](https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en)

Conflict of interests→“The beneficiaries **must take all measures to prevent any situation** where the **impartial** and **objective implementation** of the Agreement **could be compromised** for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest.

Recruitment and working conditions

Obligation to take measures to implement the **European Charter for Researchers** and **Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (best effort obligations).**

The beneficiaries must ensure that researchers and third parties involved in the action are aware of them. <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r>

Adjustments and Budget transfers

Za vse spremembe, kjer ni potreben amandma, je dobro, da imaš pisno potrditev od project officer-ja in ne zgolj odobritev koordinatorja.

Za nekatere spremembe je potreben amandma, za nekatere ne. Dobro preveriti!

Deliverables and reports
